

The status of brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys*, in Bucharest area

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Abstract The brown marmorated stink bug *Halyomorpha halys* (Stal) (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) was on the alert list of European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO) from 2008 until 2013. *Halyomorpha halys* is a major polyphagous pest mainly of fruit trees and vegetables, field crops as corn and soybean and some ornamental plants and weeds and became in the last two decades a threatening invasive pest in USA. In Europe was first captured in a light trap in 2004 in Liechtenstein and afterward in 2007 in Switzerland and its evolution stayed unnoticed until 2015, when major damages were reported mainly by Italy, where despite all control measures the pear crops in some regions were totally destroyed. In Romania, the pest was first time described in 2015, following its discovery in Bucharest in September 2014, in Botanical Garden of Bucharest. The authors of that first report in Romania state that the entrance in the country could happen at least 1-2 years before, due to the fact that individuals of *Halyomorpha halys* were found in a range of several kilometers. Our observations in Bucharest area in 2015 show an alarming exponential spreading of the stink bug in the capital area, as well in some particular places all around the country. In 2016, in the USAMV Bucharest corn testing fields, goji testing fields, jujube experimental field and edible roses testing fields, *Halyomorpha halys* and *Nezara viridula* were always observed in cohabitation and they produced crop losses of 100% to goji crop, starting with the month of august and major quality depreciation in the corn field. On jujube experimental field and edible roses testing field, the adults of *H. halys* were observed since early September, without major damages. The pest also started to become a nuisance pest, many people complaining about its presence in the houses or public transportation.

Key words

brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys*, invasive pest, nuisance pest

Halyomorpha halys (Stal) (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) is one of the most menacing invasive species that spread from Asia to US and Europe in the last 20 years and according to some scientists, it can be considered “a devastating invasive species in the USA” (30). As for any other stink bug, on the feeding point usually necrotic areas and suberifications occurs, while the pulp of some fruits may become deliquescent, probably due to the destructive enzymes that are injected simultaneously while extracting the pulp liquids (32). Feeding in the growing phenophase known as shuck split or petal fall in peaches and apples cause fruit abscission (28).

Having its original roots in Eastern Asia, more exactly China, Japan, Taiwan and South Korea, the brown marmorated stink bug (BMSB) first conquered the United States (22). The first individuals were captured in 1996, in Adams Islands, Allentown (22, 27) and the species was first time identified in 2001. It

is now found in at least 42 states within the United States and the District of Columbia (32). The BMSB is a highly polyphagous pest, with more than 120 host plant species (3), while the crop losses may easily reach 100%. According to Leskey, 2012, only in the mid-Atlantic (USA) apples orchards alone, the pest pressure caused in the year 2010 losses of \$37 million, while some stone fruit growers lost more than 90% of their stone fruit crop (21). The cost of all invasive species in the United States is estimated at more than \$120 billion, while the direct damages produced by the invasive insects reach annually the amount of \$13.5 billion and the cost of pesticide to manage those insects adds another \$1.2 billion to the total amount (Farquhar 28-30). It has to be stated that the economic negative consequences of the invasive species are not limited to the agricultural losses they produce (9). As an example, USDA spent in 2010 nearly \$1.09 million only on research dedicated to the BMSB (8). *H. halys*

overwinters as adults, commonly in artificial structures like houses, which makes it one of the major nuisance insects of the present time (27), allergic reactions and dermatitis being mentioned (2), beside the unpleasant effect of the bad smell. In Maryland, in 2011, from a single 2 floors house, in 181 days 26.205 adults were collected (23).

In Europe the first adults were captured in a light trap in Liechtenstein in 2004 (11, 26), but they were not identified until 2007, when the same species individuals were found in five different places in Zurich, Switzerland, on various exotic ornamental shrubs (10, 34). Because at the beginning the BMSB was easily mistaken with *Rhaphigaster nebulosa* or other species, Wyniger and Kment, in 2010, published a key for the correct identification of *Halyomorpha halys* and its differentiation by other 11 similar appearing stink bugs found in Central Europe, including pictures of the head and pronotum (with details of corium and conexivum) and dorsal view of all 12 species. After Switzerland, BMSB was found in Germany, in 2011, in the city of Konstanz (Baden-Württemberg) (12), in Grece, in 2011, causing nuisance to Athens residents (14), in Italy, in 2012, in the region of Emilia-Romagna, Modena province (11), in France in 2012, in Alsace region (12), in Hungary, in 2013, in Buda Arboretum in Budapest (13) in Romania, in 2014, in the Botanical Garden of Bucarest (16), in Russia, in 2014, in Sochi, Krasnodar region (17) in Austria in 2015, in Vienna (15, 20), in Serbia, in 2015, at Vršac and Jevremovac Botanical Garden in Belgrade (18, 33). Until the present moment, it seems that the most affected country is Italy where the BMSB was silently spreading until 2015, as no major damages or crop losses were noticed in 2013 and 2014. In 2015, in the regions of Modena, Reggio Emilia and Bologna, the first severe damages to pear, apricot, plums, peach, apple, persimmon and tomatoes were registered, despite all the control measures applied (5, 19) and Italy is considering today *Halyomorpha halys* as the next threat of fruit growing sector.

In Romania, in 2015 Macavei *et al.* described the firsts this species, found in Bucharest in September 2014, but they state that its presence could date back to at least 1-2 years ago, due to the fact that individuals were found at several kilometers away. No severe crop losses were mentioned until now in Romania.

An accurate pest management program for BMSB should be fundamented by precise determination of the pest density and adapted pest sampling methods need to be found in order to establish the potential for economic crop loss and the economic thresholds (31). In the BMSB case, the adults and the nymphs have a sudded reaction and at the slightest disturbance either drop imediatly to the ground either the adults fly (1). This behavior significantly reduce the effectiveness of the traditional sweep net samplings or ground cloth sampling methods (1). In 2013 and 2014, in Virginia, Delaware and Maryland, Aigner *et al.* tried a different

sampling methods; they made a visual plant inspection that consisted of counting the number of brown marmorated stink bug nymphs and adults seen on soybean plants in a 2 minute inspection period while walking carefully between two rows. Compared with the traditional net sweeps, the visual inspection appears to be an effective method for assessing the BMSB populations in soybeans (1). In 2016 Blaauw *et al.* proved that the border spray applications are the most effective, as the majority of the BMSB adults and larvar instars tend to migrate to the field borders. This finding may reduce the overall insecticide sprayed quantity and contribute to the beneficial entomofauna for that specific agro-system (6). As the chemical treatments seems to be efficient only to the first instars but not on the latest and on the adults, the biological control of BMSB is the alternative solution to be considerd. In 2015, Parker proved that a botanical formulation with a strain of *Beauveria bassiana* was highly efficacious against second instar larva of BMSB. Both wettable powder and the emulsifiable suspension formulations, used at a concentration of 1×10^7 conidia/mL caused 67%–80% mortality at 9 days after treatment and 95%–100% after 12 days.

During the summer and autumn of 2016 we performed multiple visual inspection in the experimental fields of University of Agronomic Science and Veterinary Medicine from Bucharest. Our findings demonstrate that *Halyomorpha halys* is a major threat also for Romania, as the observation made in the Bucharest area and Buzau area showed an exponential grow of the BMSB population since 2015. The spreading of *Halyomorpha halys* in Romania may have a huge negative impact on the corn and goji production, as well as other crops.

Materials and Methods

Our observations were made in the experimental fields of University of Agronomic Science and Veterinary Medicine from Bucharest, in corn, goji, jujube and edible roses crops and in Buzau city area. Warning leaflets about *Halyomorpha halys* were sent by email to over 200 agricultural producers and shared on LinkedIn and Facebook social networks.

The observations on corn were done on P9911 hybrid (Invincibil – FAO 410 (AQ)), cultivated on a plot of 0.25 ha at a density of 75000 plants/ha, irrigated by drip irrigation system. We consider the border area having a width of 6 m, based on bibliographical references, for the easynes of pest population estimation. The observations on goji were done on three goji berry biotypes - Biotype 1, Biotype 2 and Biotype Ua (4). Our observations focused on the determinations regarding the density of *H. halys* individuals on plants and on m², using the visual plant inspection method (1). Cissel *et al.* showd there is limited information available on which corn growth

stages are most sensitive to *H. halys* feeding or the density of BMSB that cause yield losses.

Additionally, the attack frequency, attack intensity and the attack degree caused by the BMSB was evaluated. For our calculation, we used the following formulas:

$$\text{The attack frequency } F (\%) = \frac{n}{N} \times 100$$

where N = the number of plants observed and n = the number of plants showing specific attack symptoms;

$$\text{The attack intensity } I (\%) = \frac{\sum(i \times f)}{n}$$

where i = % of plants presenting the attack symptoms, f = the number of plants with the specific % of attack, n = the total number of plants attacked;

$$\text{The attack degree } Ga (\%) = \frac{F(\%) \times I(\%)}{100}$$

where F (%) = attack frequency and I (%) = the attack intensity.

Results

The spreading of BMSB in the South East area

Until the present moment, the presence of the BMSB was confirmed all around the Bucharest city area and in the neighbouring regions from Ilfov, Giurgiu and Dâmbovița counties. The insect was found also in Buzău county, at the Vegetable Research and Development Station Buzău, as well as in the city of Buzău. Another confirmation comes from Mureș county, where it was found on a raspberry crop (Valea Izvoarelor village, 0.22 ha raspberry field). Different researchers stated that they have seen the BMSB in Cluj and Turda area, but as no insect or picture was received from those areas, we do not confirm the presence on those territories yet.

Damage to corn

Until the present moment in Romania there is no Pentatomidae pest damaging corn, so there is no determination in our literature regarding the sampling methods, the pest population evaluation or the determination of the economic threshold for any stink bug on corn and no equivalence can be made in order to approximate the critical level of BMSB density on corn plants.

In the summer of 2016, on 29.07.2016, on the irrigated corn field, we count a maximum of 12 BMSB adults on a corn plants having three ears/plant. 29 July was considered the peak of the mating period (figure 1). The BMSB on the field border was 3.4 individuals/m² while in the interior area was 1.3 individuals/m² (Table 1).

Table 1

The *Halyomorpha halys* densities evaluation, on the border and in the interior area of the experimental field

	Border area	Interior area
Plant density/ha	75000	75000
Plant density/m ²	7,5	7,5
Area (m ²)	900	1665
Number of plants/area	7200	13320
BMSB medium density/plant	3,4	1,3
BMSB medium density/m ²	25,5	9,75
Total BMSB individuals	24480	17316
Total BMSB individuals on experimental field		41796

Two species of stink bugs have been seen living in cohabitation: *Nezara viridula* and *Halyomorpha halys*. This habit might be the misleading factor in the late identification of *H. halys* specimens in Romania, as the

N. viridula hibernating forms resemble somehow with *H. halys*. Ten days after the mating peak period, the second generation of *H. halys* larvae were noticed (figure 2).

Fig. 1. Aspects of *Halyomorpha halys* presence on corn. a. adults on cob; b. *N. viridula* and *H. Halys* cohabitation; c. mating period (29.07.2016)

Fig. 2. *Halyomorpha halys* eggs and first instar nymphs, cluster around a mass of newly-hatched eggs on the underside of a corn leaf (09.08.2016)

The damage on corn kernels is specific, all the attacked kernels having visible feeding points and a dehydrated, yellow-faded colour in the kernel milk

stage (R3) and kernel dough stage and become blackish and present visible white areas with a blackish contour at the harvest maturity (R7) (figure 3 and 4).

Fig. 3. The aspect of attacked corn ears, at harvest maturity stage

Fig. 4. Details of the *Halyomorpha halys* attack on corn kernels

Damage to goji berry

On goji, the first BMSB 4 and 5 instars and adults were found in the middle of June (figure 5), but their presence was considered harmless. Starting middle of

July, the larvae of *H. Halys* started to produce damages to the goji crop, but still the first goji harvest seemed to be unaffected (02.08.2016).

Fig. 5. The different *Halyomorpha halys* generations feeding on goji (18.07.2016)

The density of the BMSB individuals on goji plants differ with the date and the size of the plant. Between 19 and 47 adults and larvae were found on a plant. Currently there is no determination of economic threshold for goji crop, but as the adults and larvae are very mobile, we consider that more than 5 individuals on one goji plant can lead to important losses.

The attack frequency F(%) was 100% starting with 17 June until 9 September, as each of the goji plants had different larval instars or adults on them and starting to decrease afterwards. The attack intensity reached 100 % also in the second half of the month of August, when no fruit was edible.

Fig. 6. Completely damaged goji berries (07.09.2016)

In the middle of August, the attack of the BMSB started to be devastating and no berry left untouched for the second harvest (figure 6). As the larvae and adults are very mobile and the fruits were completely emptied of their fluids, the attack degree was estimated to 100%, a figure that is exceptionally found in agriculture. Starting with 15 October, the presence of the BMSB on goji plants became harmless again, as the adults stop feeding and start looking for the overwintering shelter.

As in the corn fields, *N. viridula* and *H. halys* species of stink bugs were observed in cohabitation.

Damage to jujube crop

On jujube experimental field, the adults of *H. halys* were observed in early September, but no damage could be described. A reason for this might be the fact that the jujube fruits start to ripen in the first decade of September and the fruit epidermis was already too difficult to be penetrated.

Conclusions

The spreading of *Halyomorpha halys* in Bucharest area could be appreciated having an exponential growth, as from the 25 individuals collected in 2014, mentioned by Macavei *et al.*, we have spotted at least 40 thousands individuals in 2016, thus immediate control measures are imposed. The corn crop seems to be one of the most threatened crops in Romania, together with tomatoes (farmers, personal communication, October 2016). The goji crop is also very exposed, but luckily it is not a major agricultural crop in Romania.

The observations on *H. halys* biology should continue, as it is uncertain if already the second generation occurs in the exceptional climatic condition of 2016 (latest eggs found on 17 August on apple) or there was just an overlap of the pest generations.

Careful observations should be carried out on the characteristics of the cohabitation habit between *Nezara viridula* and *Halyomorpha halys*.

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